

Appendix. Affective Reading Literacy Review: Summary of findings

Authors	Year	Title	Focus	Type of study	Method	Results	Affective literacy practices	Educational level / Participants	Language involved	Place of study	Concept of affective literacy
Abdul Rahim & Lee	2017	Proposing an affective literacy framework for young learners of English in Malaysian rural areas: Its key dimensions and challenges	Professional development of English teachers considering the affective dimension of language teaching.	Research study	Qualitative approach. Data gathered through (1) audio-taped interview sessions, and (2) video-taped class observations. A qualitative content analysis was carried out to collect teachers' opinions and needs related to language teaching.	Teacher training is essential in literacy development. The level of confidence and need for support required by teachers depends on their knowledge and training: well-trained teachers display better classroom management skills more effective strategies, and greater student engagement furthermore. The need for teacher training increases when students have limited exposure or experience with the target language. The authors propose an "Affective Literacy Framework for Rural Young Learners (ALFRYL)".	Teaching resources mentioned: songs, stories, rhymes, humour and elements of fun.	4 elementary teachers (2 of them are "non-optionist" - not trained to teach English)	EFL*	Malasya	Affective dimension of language teaching and use; based on Cole's (2008) definition of affective literacy: "the ability to communicate and respond to phenomena on the affective level". Other key concepts in the study: affective mediation (the involvement of the teacher to motivate learners); "Teacher-initiated affective interaction pedagogies".
Ahmed, A., & Morgan, B.	2021	Postmemory and multilingual identities in English language teaching: a duoethnography	Exploration of the social and affective influences of postmemory on multilingual identity in schools, to recopceptualize the concept of "multilingual identity" as something dynamic that depends on ethnicity, race, gender, and student's (post)memories.	Research study	Duoethnography: a dialogic and iterative methodology, in which two or more researchers compare and contrast their lived experiences. The dialogue brings about unexpected topics and allows a deeper understanding.	Pedagogical implications for language education that seek to foster critical affective literacies. Turning to affect and emotion when discussing about multilingual identities. Pedagogical attention to memory, affect and identity to have a better understanding of teachers' and students' agency and multilingual semiotic practices.	Learning to read religious classicals; using creative digraphia; reading multilingual signages in urban spaces; or learning a heritage language, in order to form a multilingual identity.	2 university teachers of EAP*	Participant s' L1* and ESL*	Canada	Critical Affective Literacy (CAL) defined by Anwaruddin (2016) (see below). CAL* as mobiliser of "multimodal, compositional resources to convey meaning and emotion in respect to English" (p. 11).

Ahmed, A., Morgan, B. & Maciel, R. F.	2021	Feeling our Way: A Trioethnography on Critical Affective Literacy for Applied Linguistics	Exploration of the "potency of affect and emotionality of texts to encounter misinformation and myside bias". Mobilisation of affective literacies (affect and identity) in ELT* multilingual contexts.	Research study	Duoethnography (see Ahmed and Morgan, 2021)	The potential of duoethnography to enable critical reflective pedagogy in post-secondary English for Academic Purposes (EAP) contexts; it allows for meaning-making beyond acquisition of mis/ information and mobilizes affect/emotion for social justice. Fostering enhanced affective awareness implies a different way of teaching, less based on formal curricula, more on experiential activities. Introducing affect also helps Ls understand the others; and search for the common good.	Three examples in different contexts: (1) EAP*, use of duoethnography methodology in a collaborative research and writing project for ESL students in order to mobilize affect/emotion for social justice; (2) Language Teacher Education, in a pre-service English language teaching education course students have to "develop a "blueprint for action" (e.g., a new policy, curriculum innovation, [...] materials, workshop for teachers etc.) based on a sociopolitical or identity-based gap/bias in the ELT field" (pp. 547-548); (3) English for Medical Purposes, leaners are asked to reflect on how language plays an important role in humanizing medicine.	3 university teachers of EAP	Participant s' L1 (English, Portugues e) and ESL	Canada and Brazil	CAL framework, 4 principles. One: examining why we feel what we feel, Two: striving to enter a relation of affective equivalence, Three: interrogating the production and circulation of objects of emotion in everyday politics, and Four: focusing on the performativity of emotions to achieve social justice.
Anwaruddin, S. M. (aka Ahmed, A.)	2016	Why critical literacy should turn to 'the affective turn': making a case for critical affective literacy	Inclusion of Affective Literacy to Critical Literacy. New Concept of Critical Affective Literacy (CAL). Focus on objects of emotion that label some political subjects as more or less deserving of compassion and care.	Theoretical perspective	-	CAL framework based on 4 principles: 1. Examining why we feel what we feel. ("towardness-awayness"). 2. Striving to enter a relation of affective equivalence or empathy. 3. Interrogating the production or circulation of objects of emotions in everyday politics 4. Focusing on the performativity of emotions to achieve social justice.				Canada	CAL as transformative pedagogy; considers the literacy skills and practices that are needed for dynamic and evolving societal needs and changes.

Bacon, H. R., Rolim, P. & Humaidan, A.	2022	"I Don't Feel I'm Capable of More": Affect, Literacy, Dis/Ability	Engaging the affective disruptions of difficult experiences of a disabled adult woman (Diana) and their emotional residue over time; addressing the multiplicity of Diana's subjectivities through conversations.	Research study	Single-case retrospective study, qualitative study that explores difficult experiences in schooling, literacy and life of an adult woman	Researchers advocate for a new "materialist approach to literacy research and critical dis/ability studies can powerfully frame research that calls out injustice and cultivates hope" (p. 51). The approach to Diana's experiences exposes the consequences of school literacy practices that can limit possibilities for learners to make connections and grow. Diana's stories elucidate the importance of educational spaces for adults who were marginalized by their school histories and lived experiences.		Diana, age 25, a disabled adult woman, White divorced mother of two	English as L1	USA	"Affect in teaching, learning, and life experiences is impacted by intensities and capacities of moments and events in time and space to produce movements, change, and relations, such as happiness, envy, shame, or anxiety, that affect bodies in different ways" (p. 52). Importance of affect in relation to felt experiences and emotional intensities.
Beauchemin, F. & Qin, K.	2023	Bilingual teachers and young children co-constructing affect and play in translanguaging read-alouds	Teacher training; developing teacher candidates' culturally and linguistically sustaining literacy instruction.	Research study	Multiple-case study design; discourse analytic approach; a cross-case synthesis analysis approach. Four types of data were collected: (1) the lesson plan co-created by the participants, (2) the video-recordings of each participant's teaching of the read-alouds, (3) the stimulated recall interviews -we interviewed the teachers by playing the video recording of their teaching and asking them to discuss their instructional decisions and (4) the participants' written reflection of their teaching.	"Affect figures into the process of literacy instruction and translanguaging read-alouds can afford bilingual children opportunities to playfully engage with the text that centers their cultural epistemologies" (p. 191). The practices presented in the study leverages children's full linguistic repertoire and funds of knowledge.	Use of a bilingual picturebook; co-design of read-alouds for bilingual students and individual implementation of read-alouds; embodied performance and translanguaging.	2 Mexican-American bilingual pre-service elementary teachers enrolled in a teacher education program.	ESL and Spanish (heritage language)	USA	"Notion of affect as relational and performed forces that emerge from the in-betweenness among people, objects and material and discursive context" (p. 191). CAL as the use of texts that "privilege the ways of being and doing of the dominant social groups and marginalize those of the others" (p. 195).

Boldt, G. & Leander, K.M.	2020	Affect theory in reading research: Imagining the radical difference	Reorientation of reading research when Affect theory is considered: how reading and literacy move in people's lives.They are concerned with the ways literacy becomes vital in the life of a person.	Theoretical perspective	Reflection on affect understood as affecting and being affected. Spinoza's view on the impact created as one "body" acts upon another. Proposal of Deleuze-Guattarian 4 key tenets: (1) materials come into nonhierachical, rhizomatic relations on a "plateau"; (2) relational are non-representational; (3) affect is the property of relations and not of the individual person; (4) affective relations can be more deterritorializing or territorializing.	Analyses of "intensities" = reading as it is created through specific sets of affective relations with other elements/people. Disruptions concerning the individual, inside/outside divisions/representation s human-non-human binaries. Re-orientations for reading research: (1) text as a door to a world of relations/not what text means but what text does; (2) creation of "personal meaning" connections; (3) reading research as embodied attunement attending the emergent relations of readers, texts, and material worlds and moving with them; and (4) reading intervention as creating affective intensities.				USA	Affective literacy: how "people, objects, ideas,words, feelings, senses, spaces, histories, and cultures – come together in nonhierarchical relations" to create and recreate meaning-making while reading. Affective literacy is distinct from critical literacy in that the social and cultural values that are explored through its implementation, do not necessarily engage with a discriminated group (Cole, 2009,p.74).
Cartun, A. & Dutro, E.	2020	The Humanizing Potential of Risky Writing: Tracing Children's and Teacher Candidates' Critical-Affective Literacy Practices	Inclusion of testimony and critical witness as an example of critical affective practice to foster literacy experience.	Research study	Qualitative study. Data collected from: audio recordings of research team meetings and; filming of methods class, preservice teachers lesson enactment; artifacts created during the course: reflections, writing assignments, lesson plans; and interviews with the preservice teachers and their writing buddies. Coding and qualitative analysis of materials in search for elements of the theories and pedagogies used.	The critical-affective pedagogies, such as enacting a pedagogy of testimony and critical witness, can foster and support these moments by inviting shared vulnerability and risk-taking.	Use of video, interviews and writing artifacts to develop writing	2 elementary preservice teachers and 2 children (their writing buddies)	L1	USA	Affect as a "sensations of experience that cannot be named as emotion <i>and</i> is inclusive of those labelled feelings; affect brings us viscerally into the present moment <i>and</i> is always spilling over with the resonance of the past and the potential of the future" (p.5). CAL as a pedagogical tool of addressing human vulnerability, thus, educators can raise new questions and extend the ethical field in which educators and students move.

Dernikos, B. P., Nightengale-Lee, B., Thiel, J. J., Lenters, K. & Bailey, E.	2023	Theorizing Literacies as Affective Flows: Attuning to the Otherwise Possibilities of Hip-Hop's "In-the-Red Frequencies	How meaning-making, literacies, identities, power, privilege, and in/equities are entangled with/in non/human sociomaterial force relations. Inspired by Rose, they build theoretically on the philosophical principles of hip-hop—flow, rupture, layering, and sampling.	Theoretical perspective		Classrooms as more-than-human "places-in-the-making", where cultural flows (e.g., of mate-only, histories) occur within school structures.				USA	Affective Mobilities in Relation to Blackness. The concept of relations as complex mobile network of more-than-human relationalities that include sounds, thoughts, images, histories, spaces, identities, ideologies, feelings, etc.
Guichot, E. & De Sarlo, G.	2023	Affective literature, effective literacy: a case of affect turn among preservice teachers in Spain	LTE. Implementation of interventions that relate to emotions and literature to develop different aspects in the field of language and literature teaching.	Research study	A mixed-method methodology was used, facilitating data triangulation. Questionnaire (consisting of 10 items grouped into two dimensions: the teaching and learning process of language and literature and the emotional dimension, the subjects expressed their level of agreement with the achievement of different objectives after the intervention; and evaluation of students learning diaries, composed of the narratives of the experiences lived in practices). The diaries were analysed following Van Manen's (1990) selective reading approach.	The intervention facilitates link between affective and cognitive perspective and a new type of multimodal literacy; increase of participants' emotional competence and emotional intelligence; the teaching methodology activated a more heterodox side, according to participants; practices contributed to inclusive socio-emotional development.	Several practices are presented: spontaneous writing based on learners' memories; writing stories in pairs; multisensory storytelling; students take the roles of characters in stories they hear; description of a partner from an eclectic point of view.	University; 66 pre-service elementary school teachers	Spanish L1	Spain	Concept of "affective" focused on participants' affective reactions and vulnerability beyond institutionalized teaching practices (in line with Ehret and Dutro's conceptualization). There is an unclear distinction between emotional competence and affective literacy. Multimodal understanding of the literary artefact, that transform the concept of literacy.

Jiang, J.	2024	“Emotions are what will draw people in”: A study of critical affective literacy through digital storytelling	Fusing the theoretical understandings of multimodal pedagogy and critical affective literacy. It examines college students' affective and emotional responses to social justice issues.	Research study	Qualitative case study: semi-structured interviews with 11 students, observing the students' multimodal composition processes, and reviewing the students' digital storytelling videos.	Participants performed critical emotional actions when creating digital stories to draw the public's attention to social justice issues.	Design of storytelling videos	11 first-year college students	English L1	USA	CAL (see Anwaruddin, 2016); and multimodality as a form of embodied learning and assessment that allows the expression of feelings and sensations.
Keegan, P.	2021	Critical affective civic literacy: A framework for attending to political emotion in the social studies classroom	How to educate civic education students in political emotion	Theoretical perspective		Inclusion of critical emotion studies, affective citizenship, and agonistic political theory in civic education studies.				USA	Critical affective literacy in civic education classrooms. The topics of emotion and affect are of interest as they are untheorized, their role in the process of teaching and learning social studies still to be uncovered. Emotional injunctions in pluralistic societies that explain how the 'affective citizen' is constructed in schools: concept of otherness, coping with difference and embracing otherness. Existence of feelings of discomfort (hate, fear, shame) that need to be educated. Besides fear, emotions like love and compassion can also harm and essentialize migrant, refugee, or asylum-seeking youth, by categorizing them as pitiable and vulnerable (Anwaruddin, 2017).

Kole, K.	2018	The role of fairy tales in affective learning: Enhancing adult literacy and learning in FE* and community settings	Improvement of cognitive, linguistic and creative writing to enhance literacy and wellbeing through the narrative quest of fairy tales.	Research study	Mixed-method pre-post study. Data collected from: discussions, interviews and written assignments. Questionnaire. Pre-post analysis of participants' writings. Participants' literacy levels were ascertained through a BKSBS standardised diagnostic assessment tool, which identified literacy levels and measured linguistic competency.	Participants improved their understanding of symbolism and metaphor with the story, increased their understanding of figurative language, improved linguistic skills, and cognitive abilities, and enhanced problem-solving, self-esteem, and personal well-being.	The use of fairy tales to understand the symbolic meaning as a scaffold for exploring problem-solving, well-being, identity, and literacy.	Adult learners in Further Education	L1	Australia	New Literacy Study theory of literacy as a social practice to improve cognitive, linguistic and creative writing skills; enhancement of literacy skills, problem-solving and affective learning.
Mayes, E. & Center, E.	2003	Learning with student climate strikers' humour: towards critical affective climate justice literacies	Use of humour for climate justice education.	Practical application	Study and creation of multimodal texts to encourage climate justice	Humour as a potent resource in affirmative contention and promotion of emotion.	Analysis and creation of puns, slogans, signs, jokes, etc to promote creative writing	Young adults	L1	Australia	Critical affective climate justice literacy.
Morgan, B. & Ahmed, A.	2023	Teaching the Nation(s): A Duoethnography on Affect and Citizenship in a Content-Based EAP Program	Exploration of participants' experiences and emotional attachments to nationhood, reflecting on their influences on teaching around language and citizenship.	Research study	Duoethnography (see Ahmed and Morgan, 2021)	The study shows the importance of critical affective literacies to expand the pedagogical repertoires of EAP teachers and students in a time of resurgent nationalism.	They present 2 examples: Collaborative writing in which learners play multiple roles as co-authors, tutors and peer-reviewers, among others; and an assignment on service-learning or volunteerism, that encourages critical inquiry into national narratives of Canada as a generous and benevolent society.	2 University EAL educators	EAP*	Canada	CAL and emotional attachment to nationhood

Perry, M.	2020	Pluriversal literacies: affect and relationality in vulnerable times	Systemic dimensions of practice that create and perpetuate inequities. Pluriversal literacies: not literacies of any particular place, topic, or people; rather, they are a practice of making sense and forming actions in relation to an always emerging global context.	Theoretical perspective		Literacy becomes plural: visual, artifactual, and digital. Literacies become relative practices as we recognize that we do not make meaning in an individualized vacuum: critical, community, cultural, racial, and multiple. Literacies become physical: without divide between mind and body, human and nonhuman: embodied, material, and place.				UK	Affective literacy/pluriversal literacies connect people with knowledge, influence, structures, infrastructures, and ways of thinking and being. Global literacy education to support multiple ways of making meaning and engaging in our shared world	
Romero, E. & Bobkina, J.	2023	Including diversity through cinema-based affective literacy practices: A case study with EFL/ESL pre-service teachers	LTE. Implementation of affective literacy practices in the classroom to help future students build intercultural capacities and empathy towards migration.	Research study	Qualitative study. Semi structured interviews. Data from transcribed recordings analysed using a content analysis approach; design and implementation of a workshop to develop affective literacy practices.	Success of experience, 5 main topics identified: emotional education, critical thinking, intercultural awareness, communication practice, and interaction.	Implementation of trailer-based affective literacy practices in the intercultural classroom, used as a pedagogical tool to help their future students build their intercultural capacities, involving all their senses and exploring their feelings.	49 pre-service teachers from the Master's programme in EFL/ESL	Teacher Training	EFL	Spain	CAL: "social justice and affective practices in the language teaching curriculum implies teaching students to work with texts more actively and reflectively to better understand power, in/equality and in/justice in human relations" (p. 860). Affective literacy practices into critical literacy-based language teaching. Use of multimodal texts in a digitally-based society.
Santos, K.	2020	Queer Affective Literacies: Examining "Rotten" Women's Literacies in Japan	The impact Boys Love literacies have on readers	Practical application	Analysis of Boys love literacies, especially women's fan comic	The power of Boys Love as an affective resource in minority group of readers' engagement	The teaching of rotten literacies through fanworks	Adult women	L1		Japan	Affective literacy engages readers to the book

Suh, Y. & Huh, S.	2023	An EFL Model of Critical Literacies: Adapted and Reshaped from Previous Studies	Creation of an EFL model of Critical Literacies	Theoretical perspective	Review of Critical Literacy & Pedagogy of Multiliteracies= without language focus. Review of models that adapt to foreign language learners' proficiency needs= cognitive-skill based models without emotions and morality.					Korea	Model for English as a foreign language that includes conventional skill-based literacy, critical affective literacy and adds intercultural citizenship education
Tadiar, N.	2009	Affective literacy, democratization and war	How to explore ways to draw attention to the translocal affective subspaces in popular lament songs	Practical application	The inclusion of Philippine popular lament songs show globally an imaginative future with different political affective literacy.	Philippine popular lament song	Adults	L1		Philippine	Transnational affective literacies
Truman, S., Hackett, A., Pahl, K., McLean Davies, L. & Escott, H.	2021	The Capaciousness of No: Affective Refusals as Literacy Practices	The affective potential that emerges from saying no to literacy practices. How attention to affect ruptures humanist logics that inform normative approaches to literacy.	Theoretical perspective	Reflections by considering different "bodies": teacher, who quit in their first year, a silent child, a poet who refused to write, and crumpled paper in a bin.					Australia and UK	Refusals = affective moment. attention to nonconscious, noncognitive, and transindividual bodily forces and capacities. Affect deprivileges the human as the sole agent in an interaction, thus disrupting measurements of who counts as a literate subject and what counts as a literacy event.

*Acronyms:

CAL - Critical Affective Literacy
EAP - English for Academic Purposes
EFL - English as a Foreign Language
ELT - English Language Teaching
ESL - English as a Second Language
L1 - Mother tongue
LTE - Language Teacher Education
FE- Further education